

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№5

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Elektron nashr. 1839 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-mayda ruxsat etildi.

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golischeva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.11 Marketing
08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
08.00.13 Menejment
08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

“Zavur kollektor suvlarining kimyoviy tarkibi tahlili va ularni tozalash zarurati (Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi misolida)”.....	20
Kungiratbay Sharipov, Ma‘ruf Nurmanov	
Forming demand and stimulating sales in Uzbekistan.....	26
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Членство в ВТО как драйвер развития: взгляд Узбекистана через призму опыта Вьетнама и Казахстана.....	30
Ж.Я.Нуриллаев	
Mamlakatimizda tizimli ahamiyatga molik banklarni aniqlash tartibi va ularning bank tizimi moliyaviy barqarorligiga ta‘sirini tahlili.....	37
Xolmamatov Farhodjon Kubaevich	
O‘zbekiston respublikasida aholi bandligini ta‘minlashdagi dolzarb masalalar	44
Ibragimov Elmurod Gulboynor o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekiston respublikasida elektr energiyasi ta‘minoti hajmini yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmiga ta‘sirini ekonometrik tahlil qilish.....	48
Fayziyev Rabim Alikulovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tijorat banklarining xizmat turlarini takomillashtirish amaliyoti	60
Umurzoqova Adiba Ochilovna	
Qishloq xo‘jaligi kooperativi boshqaruv tizimida buxgalteriya hisobini tashkil qilishning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari	67
Abduraxmanov Ramazon Abdullayevich	
O‘zbekistonda qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlari umumiy hajmini prognozlashda ekonometrik modellar (yillik)	72
Qodirov Farxod Amirovich, Bo‘ribaeva Qundiz Muratbaevna	
Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari xavfsizligi tizimini takomillashtirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari.....	77
Mahamatova Maftuna	
Xufiyona va yashirin iqtisodiyotning amaliy tahlili o‘zbekiston miqyosida.....	83
Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli	
Soliq tizimini barqarorligini belgilovchi omillar tahlili.....	87
Nurillayev Jasurbek Davronbekovich	
Mahalliy budjetlar daromad manbalarini mustahkamlash omillari.....	92
Soatova Nodira Boboxanovna	
Bank infratuzilmasining raqamli transformatsiyasi va resurslar bazasi shakllanishi: nazariy asoslar va texnologik yondashuvlar.....	97
Raxmatov Azizjon Jaloliddinovich, Jumayev Muzaffar Mahmud o‘g‘li	
Ichki auditning transformatsion potentsiali: tahliliy amallarni takomillashtirish orqali samaradorlikni oshirish.....	102
Misirov Akbarali Pardaboyevich, Ismoilov Asadbek Abdusamat o‘g‘li	
Xorijiy mamlakatlarda yashil moliyalashtirishni rivojlantirish yo‘llari.....	110
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	
Yashil moliya – iqtisodiy rivojlanish mexanizmi sifatida	117
Nodir Xidirov G‘iyosaliyevich	
Xo‘jalik yurituvchi subyektlarning likvidiligi va moliyaviy barqarorligini ta‘minlashning xorij tajribasi va uning amaliy ahamiyati	122
Bauyetdinov M.J.	
Теоретические подходы к определениям агрессий социально - экономической и политической стабильности государства как фактор повышения рекреационных потребностей	128
Алимова Райхона Баходировна	
Innovatsion ta‘lim texnologiyalari asosida talabalarning metodik tayyorgarligini shakllantirish.....	139
Komilov Umidjon Normurod o‘g‘li, Tulyaganova Gulnoza Olimjon qizi	

Kichik biznes subyektlarini moliyalashtirish manbalari	143
Nematulloev Suxrob Sobirovich	
Bir qatlamli elastik asosda joylashgan to'sinning seysmik kuchlar ta'siridagi tebranishining V.Z. Vlasov usuli asosida analitik tadqiqi	148
Kamola Xaydarova	
"Sibir daryolarining burilishi" loyihasining tarixiy va retrospektiv tahlili	153
Mahmudov Nosir Mahmudovich	
Sarguzasht turizmini rivojlanishi va sarguzasht turlarda turistlarning xavfsizligini ta'minlashda instruktor-gidlarning roli	159
Tilovmurodov Dostonbek Furqat o'g'li	
Scientific-theoretical foundations of the use of ict in ensuring management efficiency and security in enterprises	165
Khalilov Bekzod Akhmatovich	
Tijorat banklarida kredit riskini boshqarish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	171
Mirtursunova Dinara Anvarovna	
O'zbekiston respublikasi tijorat banklarida masofaviy bank xizmatlarini joriy etishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	175
Tangriyev Izzat Raxmatullayevich	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida eko va etno turizmni rivojlantirishning istiqbollari va iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	181
Erkayeva Barno, Xushvaqto'v Ramziddin	
O'zbekiston bank tizimida raqamli valyutalar va yashil investitsiyalar integratsiyasini takomillashtirish	186
Nodirov Azizxon Asrorovich	
Global energiya noaniqligining o'zgaruvchanligi ekonomertik modellari	192
Bexzod Qo'ziboev	
Экоцифра: цифровизация МСП для зеленого устойчивого роста	197
С.С. Убаева	
Qishloq xo'jaligini barqaror rivojlantirish va ekologik toza hududni yo'lga qo'yishning ahamiyati	201
Ergashov Ulug'bek Zoxidjonovich	
Statistika fanining shakllanish bosqichlari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	206
Nabixodjaev Abbas Abdupattahovich, Umarova Mukaddas Abbasovna	
Hududlarning atmosferaga chiqaradigan zararli chiqindilar miqdorini sanoat mahsulotiga nisbati bo'yicha tahlili	210
Baqoyev Husan Nuriddinovich	
Qayta tiklanadigan vodorod narxlari strategiyasini o'rganish: xarajat noaniqliklarini bartaraf etish	216
Nuraliyeva Komila Sanakulovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligini "yashil" iqtisodiyot asosida rivojlantirishga o'tishning zarurligi va mohiyati	221
Yoldoshev Mutalib Ibrohimovich	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda "yashil investitsiyalar" dan foydalanishning xorij tajribalari	225
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna, Rustamova Nasiba Arslanovna	
Ijtimoiy iqtisodiy ehtiyojlar va ularning iqtisodiy rivojlanishdagi o'rni.....	230
Raxmonova Feruza Musaqulovna	
Oliy ta'lim xizmatlarini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotda tutgan o'rni.....	234
Mirzaxajeva Shaxzoda Shuxratovna	
Tijorat banklari muammoli kreditlarining likvidlilikka ta'siri.....	240
Karshiyev Adham Anvarovich	
Kichik firmalarning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning nazariy metodologik jihatlari.....	245
Ruzmetov Davron Ibrogimovich, Aliyev Maqsudbek Erkinovich	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarning moliyaviy resurslaridan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	251
Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna	

“Deviant xulq-atvorli o‘smirlarning ijtimoiy moslashuvining psixologik xususiyatlari”	255
Saidbekova Feruza Anvarbek qizi	
Aholi daromadlarini diversifikatsiya qilishda davlat siyosatining roli va imkoniyatlari	258
Nutfullayev Shohrux Mexli o‘g‘li, Qurbanov Ulug‘bek Erkinovich	
Анализ показателей развития зелёной химии по всему миру и в узбекистане за последние десять лет	262
Фозилова Фирангиза Комиловна	
Tijorat banklarining o‘zbekiston respublikasi iqtisodiyotiga ta’siri	270
Masharipov Rasulbek Jo‘rabekovich	
Biznes birlashuvda buxgalteriya hisobi va auditni takomillashtirish yo‘nalishlari	273
Hamroyeva Zuhra Amiral qizi, Xayitboyeva Laylo Oybekovna, Mirzarayimov Sardorbek Ravshanovich	
O‘zbekiston respublikasida pul-kredit siyosatining maqsadi	277
Adilov Zuxriddin Marip o‘g‘li	
Qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlarining ishlab chiqarish va bozorlararo aloqalarining statistik o‘zgarish tendensiyalari	281
Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	
Iqtisodiy bilimlarni shakllanishi va rivojlanishi	286
Po‘latov Abdulloh Xolxo‘jayevich	
Теоретические основы эффективного управления финансовыми ресурсами предприятий с государственной долей (на примере узбекистана)	291
Ахмедов Дилшод Турсункулович	
Robototexnika asoslari va maktab ta‘limida qo‘llanilishi	298
Tuxliyev Muslimbek Sherzod o‘g‘li	
Sun‘iy intellektlar yordamida o‘quvchilarni hayotiy faoliyat ko‘nikmasini shakllantirishi	303
Mirxasilova Zulfiya Kochkarovna, Abdurahmanova Ozoda Djo‘rayevna, Kurbanov Azimjon Jo‘raboy o‘g‘li	
Levi tengsizligi uchun A.N. Kolmogorov teoremlari	316
Saypiddinov Shukurullo Sadrdinovich, Baxramov Rustamjon Qambarali o‘g‘li	
Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar bank tizimida raqamli moliyaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish afzalliklari	320
Xodjimamedov Akmal Ashurovich, Umedov Abdullo Umedovich	
O‘zbekiston respublikasining mdh mamlakatlari bilan tashqi savdo faoliyati tahlili: o‘zgarish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari	326
Ilyosov Asrorjon Axrorjon o‘g‘li, Abdullaev Alisher Maxmudovich, Tuxtasinova Muxayyo Mirzasultonovna	
Elektron tijoratni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi	330
Madieva Zuxra Iskandarbekovna	
Inson resurslarini o‘rganishning asosiy yondashuvlari: mohiyat-ta’rifiy tahlil	336
Bakirov Qobiljon Mamatyusupovich	
Bandlikni ta’minlashda davlat tomonidan institutsional muhit yaratishning roli	340
Dilorom Tojiboyeva, Umida Ravshanovna Anvarova	
Mamlakatimizda islom moliyasini rivojlantirish maqsad va choralari	346
Xoliyorov Xomid Boynazarovich	
Разработка экспертной системы для оценки финансового состояния предприятия	352
Tajibayeva Kizlargul Ajiniyazovna	
Farg‘ona vodiysi viloyatlarida kichik biznes ko‘rsatkichlarining o‘zgarishi: panel regressiya tahlili	362
Tojiyeva Muhabbatxon Mansurjon qizi	
O‘zbekiston Respublikasida makroiqtisodiy ko‘rsatkichlarni hisoblashdagi asosiy muammolar va ularning yechimlari	368
Farmonov Ilhomjon Iqboljon o‘g‘li	
Xorijiy tajriba asosida korxonalar innovatsion faolligini boshqarishni takomillashtirish	374
Hakimova Nozimaxon Sobirjon qizi	
Mahalliy davlat hokimiyati organlarida milliy kadrlar zaxirasini shakllantirish	380
G‘aniev Elyor Sobirjonovich	
O‘zbekistonda sirkulyar iqtisodiyotga o‘tishning ahamiyati	386
Mirzayev Muzaffar Maxmudovich	

The role of international investments in greening and ecological rehabilitation of the aral sea region	392
Ospanova Feruza Bazarbaevna	
“Зеленое направление” совершенствования бухгалтерского учета	397
Ибрагимов Гайратжон Артикович	
Xarajatlarni kelib chiqish joylari va javobgarlik markazlari bo'yicha hisobga olishni takomillashtirish	403
Xamidova S.Ya.	
Mintaqalarni iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari va ularni takomillashtirish.....	409
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna	
O'zbekistonda kichik turar joy biznesini rivojlantirishda xorijiy tajribalar	414
Yo'ldashev Bekzodjon Sherzodjon o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida davlat maqsadli dasturlarini moliyalashtirish yuzasidan ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar.....	419
Shodiyev Shuhrat Sunnat o'g'li	
Qandolat mahsulotlari bozorida marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	426
Azlarova Munira Muxammad-Amin qizi	
Risk management in commercial banks, methodological approaches and practical implementation	433
Baymuratova Zina Aqilbekovna, Jarilkapova Naubaxar Paraxat qizi	
The impact of competition on economic growth: evidence from uzbekistan's automotive industry.....	439
Saydaliyeva Dilrabo Baxriddin qizi	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning oliy talim xizmatlarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni.....	444
Mirzaxadjayeva Shahzoda Shuxratovna	
Развитие производства сельскохозяйственной продукции путем развития цифровых технологий.....	450
Юсупов Мухиддин Соатович	
Tijorat banklarida loyihaviy moliyalashtirish risklarini boshqarish amaliyotini takomillashtirish	457
Berdiyev Akram O'ktamovich	
Iqtisodiy tarmoqlarni soliqqa tortish orqali investitsiya loyihalarini rivojlantirish.....	463
Sharipov Eldor Salohiddin o'g'li	
Iqtisodiyotda investitsiya va kredit salohiyatini bank faoliyatiga ta'siri.....	468
Ergashova Nilufar Sobirovna	
Qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalarining raqobatbardoshlik salohiyatini boshqarishni takomillashtirish	473
Tashmukhamedova Karima Samatovna	
Ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari va istiqbollari.....	479
Kurbanova Mohinur Xabib qizi	
Xalqaro sayohat lug'ati va uning shakllanishi.....	487
Abduxadova Zilola Djamoliddinovna	
Moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlari va uni o'zbekiston respublikasi hisob tizimini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni va ahamiyati.....	492
Quvvatov G'olibjon Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Kooperatsiyalarning tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati.....	501
Mirzayev Musurmon Umidullayevich, Ziyadullayev Ilhom Narkobilovich	
Использование методов математического моделирования при внедрении коммерческих автоматических систем	505
Курбанова Рахима, Ахмедов Мехрожжон	
Tijorat banklari kapitalidagi davlat ulushini kamaytirish yo'llari.....	511
Vasiyev Alisher Samiyevich	
Механизмы трансформации неформального сектора в официальную экономику на основе финансовых инструментов.....	515
Кошанов Абдимурат Азат ули, Муртазаев Шахрух Коньскайлиевич	

The impact of tourism on the economy of Uzbekistan	519
Xaydarova Marjona, Muxamedboyeva Muxlisa, Umarov Kamron, Usmanova Aziza	
Mintaqada gastroturizm rivojlanishining iqtisodiy asoslari va zamonaviy tendensiyalari	525
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna	
Tikuv-trikotaj korxonalari brend jozibadorligini oshirishning ilmiy-nazariy jihatlarini	535
O'rinov Akmaljon Axmadjonovich	
Bank tizimida hisobotlarni avtomatlashtirish texnologiyalari	542
Sodiqov Sanjar Saydullo o'g'li	
Engineering programs in Uzbekistan on the verge of fifth industrial revolution	547
Khasan Khankeldiyev	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarining boshqaruvini yaxshilashda korporativ madaniyatning ahamiyati	551
Akramova Nazokat Israilovna	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatining iqtisodiy taraqqiyotdagi o'rni	562
Amonov Mehridin Oromiddinovich	
O'zbekiston sanoat tarmoqlarida kooperatsiya asosida tayyor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni mahalliyashtirish tizimini takomillashtirish yo'llari	572
Xalilova Sevaraxon Alijon qizi	
Moliyaviy barqarorlikning asosiy ko'rsatkichlari va ularning tahlili	578
Urmanbekova Iroda Farxodovna	
Tijorat banklarining mamlakat iqtisodiyotida tutgan o'rnini tahlil qilish	583
Kilicheva F.B., Mengnorov A.A., Bozorova O.R.	
Bog'dorchilik tarmog'ida klasterlarni joriy qilishda yevropa tajribasini qo'llash imkoniyatlari	591
Ergashov Ulug'bek Zoxidjonovich	
To'qimachilik klasterlarini boshqarishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi	598
Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich	
Barriers to tourism infrastructure development in uzbekistan: a critical analysis	605
Sarvinoz Shodmonova	
Xalqaro bozorda qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari raqobatbardoshligini oshirish	609
Mengnorov Almardon Abdirahmonovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasida infratuzilma loyihalarini amalga oshirishdagi risklarni boshqarish	620
Yusupova Zilola Ismoiljon qizi	
Korxonaning iqtisodiy barqarorligiga erishishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari	626
Iminova Nargizaxon Akramovna	
Qishloq joylari maishiy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida axborot resurslaridan samarali foydalanish	631
Xamdamiy Eldor Toshmurovich	
Meva-sabzavotlar eksportida transport koridorlari va vositalarini tanlash xususiyatlari	636
Yusupov Muxiddin Soatovich	
Рынок рабочей силы в узбекистане и ее воспроизводство	644
Шакиров Амаль Улугбекович, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахаровна	
Деньги и их функции в экономике	650
Мурадиллаев Мансур Мехроживич, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахаровна	
Развитие сельского хозяйства в узбекистане	654
Махмудов Алишер Мухтарович, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахаровна	
Инвестиции и инновации в химической промышленности узбекистана: современные тенденции и перспективы	658
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович, Султанходжаев Аманулла Асадуллаевич	
Tijorat banklari aktivlarini boshqarishni takomillashtirish	666
Mardonova Shoxsanam Baxodirovna	
Definition of agritourism as a multifunctional development in rural areas	672
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani ugli	
Kameral soliq tekshiruvida smart texnologiyalarini ma'lumotlarini soliq organlarining ma'lumotlar bazasida shakllanishi	680
Qurbonov Muxiddin Abdullaevich	
Проблемы регулирования государственно-частного партнерства и рекомендации по их решению (на примере безработицы в республике узбекистан)	687
С.Э. Холмуратов	

Автоматизация аудиторских процедур с использованием искусственного интеллекта.....	692
Ходжарахманова Назира Бахтияр кизи	
Past karbonli iqtisodiyotga o'tish zaruriyati va uning omillari.....	701
Valiyev Axliddin Aropitdinovich	
Yengil sanoatda zamonaviy tikuv mashina-kichik robotlarning mexanizmlarini mukammallashtirish	705
Sirojova Muxabbat Sodiq qizi, Kurbanov Fazliddin Aminovich	
Jismoniy shaxslar daromadlarini soliqqa tortish tizimining institutsional va iqtisodiy asoslari	710
Kuzieva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Bobomuratova Manzura Panji qizi	
Foyda solig'i bo'yicha bo'nak to'lovlarni to'lash tartibi.....	717
Yangieva N.S.	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik subyektlarini soliqlar vositasi qo'llab-quvvatlashning amaldagi holati	722
Turanboyev Boburjon Qodirjon o'g'li	
Motivation, goal-setting, and organizational performance: a case study from uzbekistan's chemical industry	726
Mamataliev Anvar Ergashevich, Bobur Urinov	
Применение искусственного интеллекта при организации налогового администрирования узбекистана	733
Н.А. Артиков	
Ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish zaruriyatini keltirib chiqaruvchi omillar.....	737
Sharofiddinova Gulnoza Iloxmonovna	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning tijorat banklari samaradorligiga ta'siri	745
Maksudov Avazbek Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Suv tanqisligi sharoitida yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish asoslari	750
Qosimov Maxamatjon Sulaymanovich	
Rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotda raqamli va raqamli bo'lmagan korxonalar tahlili	761
Raxmonov Nodirjon Raxmonjon o'g'li	
Aholining o'rtacha umr ko'rish yoshini o'zgarishi sharoitida keksalarning ijtimoiy ta'minotiga xavflarning ortishi.....	767
Toyirov Shohboz Ziyodullo o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida moliyaviy nazorat samaradorligini ta'minlash ichki nazorat xizmatlari	773
Xaydarov Baxrom Xolmuradovich	
Moliya bozorida xususiy banklar faolligini ta'minlash istiqbollari	777
Abduqahhorov Asilbek Ahror o'g'li	
Budjet daromadlari ijrosini ta'minlashda soliqlar hisobi va tahlilining ahamiyati.....	782
Abdullaev Abror Bozarboevich	
Aholi daromadini oshirish yo'llari.....	803
Shadmanov Baxodir Sherkulovich	
Tourism and regional identity in Uzbekistan: balancing heritage and development	808
Raximova Nilufar Aminovna, Abdukholikova Farida Erkinjon qizi	
O'zbekiston sanoat korxonalarining fond bozorida ishtiroki tahlil va muammolari.....	815
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
O'zbekistonda davlat-xususiy sheriklik loyihalarini moliyalashtirish va amalga oshirish tahlili	823
Karabaev Sanjar Abdusamatovich	
Globalashuv sharoitida milliy korxonalarining eksport salohiyatini boshqarish masalalari	832
Qodirov Humoyun Tolibjon o'g'li	
Бизнес-планирование и прогнозирование деятельности организации.....	836
Алимов Бехзоджон Наврузжонович	
Farg'ona vodiysida ekoturizm – kambag'allikka qarshi kurashning yangi imkoniyatlari	840
Soliyeva Nilufar Muxtorjon qizi	
Aholi turmush darajasi baholash bo'yicha dasturiy ta'minot ishlab chiqishda horij tajribasini o'rganish	844
Tursunov Farxod Baxodir o'g'li	
Mintaqa aholi turmush farovonligiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar tasnifini ishlab chiqish.....	848
Xodjanijazov Shohruh Yuldashovich	
Xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari menejmentining nazariy jihatlarini va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	856
Karimov Ulug'bek Usmonovich	

Infratuzilma va bozor infratuzilmasi tushunchalarining nazariy tavsifi	861
G'aniyev Botir Baxtiyorovich	
Повышение инвестиционной привлекательности – важное условие повышения конкурентоспособности предприятий.....	865
Каримова Дилафруз Садирдин кизи	
Yevropa ittifoqi davlatlari tijorat banklarining soliq to'lovlarini amalga oshirish tartibi	870
Komolov Odiljon Sayfidinovich	
Boshqaruvda innovatsiyalarni hisobga olgan holda agrokorxonalarni davlat tomonidan rag'batlantirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari	878
Shaniyazova Zamira	
Практические аспекты применения статистических методов контроля качества на предприятиях.....	883
Усманов Илхом Ачилович, Усманов Фарзод Шохрухович	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida iqtisodiy o'sishning yangi paradigmalarini shakllantirish: nazariy asoslar va amaliy talqinlar.....	891
Alimova Guzal Abduxakimovna	
Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarini faoliyati samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlarining nazariy va metodologik tahlili	895
Qo'ziboyev Boxodir Azzamboy o'g'li	
Kutubxonalarda raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida biznes-modellarni ishlab chiqish.....	900
Ernaqulov Sunnatillo Nurali o'g'li	
To'g'ridan-to'g'ri sug'urtalash operatsiyalari bo'yicha xarajatlarni xalqaro standartlar asosida hisob va hisobotda aks ettirish uslubi-yatini takomillashtirish	905
X.A.Raximov	
Kameral soliq tekshiruvda smart texnologiyalarini ma'lumotlarini soliq organlarining ma'lumot bazasida shakllanishi.....	910
Ergashev Uyg'un Jabborovich	
Obligatsiya moliya bozori instrumenti sifatida, milliy obligatsiyalar bozori	916
Avezov Ibrohim Ilxomovich, Yaxshiboyev Jahongir Abdualimovich	
Barqaror rivojlanish doirasida ekologik, ijtimoiy va korporativ boshqaruv (ESG) ko'rsatkichlarining yashil texnologiyalar innovatsiyasiga ta'sirini baholash.....	921
Meliqo'zieva Dilrabo Muxitdin qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyot – barqaror taraqqiyotga olib boruvchi yo'l.....	925
Xalilova Aziza Rustamovna	
Научно-теоретические основы экономической и эколого-экономической эффективности предприятий горнодобывающей промышленности.....	930
Раматов Зафарбек Жуманиязович	
Xitoyda eksport faoliyatini tashkil etishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	938
D.E.Qarshiev	
Kichik sanoat zonalarida investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirishni investitsion faollikka ta'siri.....	943
Mannapova Shaxnoza Elshodovna	
Mahalla institutining samaradorligi tahlili: so'rovnomaga yondashuvi	947
Bahriddinov Viqorjon Akbar o'g'li	
Формирование человеческого капитала в условиях демографических изменений: опыт и перспективы для узбекистана.....	955
Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи	
Farmasevtika kompaniyalari raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanish yo'nalishlari	962
Vaxrombek Bobojonov	
“Hududlarda sug'urtaga bo'lgan talabning ekonometrik tahlili” bekberganova mohira ravshonbekovna	967
O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti	
O'zbekiston va xalqaro amaliyotda raqamli marketing vositalaridan foydalanish: muammolar va yechimlar	973
Uzoqova Dilnoza Yusuf qizi	
Условия эксплуатации и экологическая безопасность автотранспортной системы на основе энергосберегающих технологий	978
Мамасалиева Мукаддас Ибадуллаевна	
O'zbekiston tibbiyot muassasalarida moliyaviy resurslardan foydalanishda xorijiy tajribalarni qo'llash.....	982
Elmurodov G'ayratjon Abdumurodovich	

Buxgalteriya hisobining samaradorligini oshirish yo'llarida zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovatsiyalar	987
Sattorov Mirjahon	
Особенности маркетинговых стратегий в условиях ограниченных ресурсов и узкой потребительской аудитории	991
Дебердиев Анвар	
DEbitorlik va kreditorlik qarzlari auditini rejalashtirish masalalari.....	995
Tulovov Erkinjon To'liqin o'g'li, Ibragimova Iroda Rashid qizi	
Инвестиционная программа узбекистана по привлечению иностранных инвестиций	1000
Камилова Наргиза Абдукажоровна, Бекмуратов Шухрат Даулетмуратович	
Turistik mahsulotni shakllantirishda turistlar hayoti xavfsizligini ta'minlash.....	1005
Rahmonov Siyovush Turob o'g'li	
Uglerodsiz energiyaga o'tishda o'zbekistonning yashil strategiya yo'l xaritasining integratsiyasi va ta'siri.....	1011
Nuraliyeva Komila Sanakulovna	
Цифровая устойчивость регионов: применение аналитики больших данных для оценки и управления экологическими рисками	1016
Маликов Шохрух Шокирович, Камалов Шухрат Камалович	
Разработка риск-ориентированной модели внутреннего контроля предприятия на этапе планирования налогов в условиях дистанционного налогового мониторинга	1024
Галеева Н.Н., Э.А.Халикова, Абдусаломова Гулчеҳра Мирзо қизи	
Анализ результатов инструментальных методов исследований у детей с врожденными пороками сердца	1029
Мухаммадиева Лола Атамурадovна	
Barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashda monetar omillardan samarali foydalanish yo'nalishlari.....	1036
Uskenbaeva Dilnoza Voxodir qizi	
Факторы повышения эффективности управления в государственном секторе.....	1043
Махмудова Севара Улугбековна	
Soliq organlari va soliq to'lovchilar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarning yangi tizimi sharoitida soliq nazorati	1048
Rajabbaeva Dildora Zakirovna, Aripova Aziza Alisherovna	
Boshqaruv jarayonlarini tashkil etishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	1053
Jo'rayeva Niginaxonim Xursand qizi	
Jahonda eksportni qo'llab-quvvatlash amaliyoti.....	1057
Xudoynazarov Sherzod Ismoilovich	
Raqamli moliyaviy texnologiyalarni korxonada darajasida joriy etish orqali moliyaviy barqarorlikka erishish strategiyasi	1063
Soibov Nozimbek Faxridin o'g'li	
Применение методов PMBOK в управлении рисками проектов	1070
Гулираъно Носирова Абдулазиз қизи	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishda aholi farovonligining o'rni va ahamiyati	1073
Bobaev Isroiljon Abdinabievich	
Вопросы инновационных инвестиций в контексте международной экономической интеграции	1078
Шарипов Бахтиёр Михлибаевич	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari hamda tendensiyalari.....	1083
Samiyev Abdurashid Qaxramonovich, Shermuxammedov Begzodjon Usmonovich	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlar samaradorligini ta'minlash yo'llari.....	1087
Nazarov Qilich Xolmuradovich	
Improving the organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of tourism in the republic of karakalpakstan	1092
Tleumuratov Baxadir Genjemuratovich	
O'zbekistonda tumanlar barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishini ta'minlash yo'llari (Surxondaryo viloyati misolida).....	1097
Qosimova Nodira Saidovna	
Innovatsion iqtisodiyotni shakllantirishning asosi sifatida innovatsiyalar.....	1102
Azizova Maliha Farrux qizi	

Влияние инвестиций на инновационное развитие и повышение конкурентоспособности экономики узбекистана	1106
Максудова Шахзода	
Возможности снижения затрат на логистику за счет цифровых технологий.....	1112
Олимова Бахора Шухратовна	
Yashil texnologiyalar va ularning iqtisodiy tizimga ta'siri.....	1116
Sultonov Omon Juma o'g'li	
Iqtisodiy o'sishning makroiqtisodiy faktorlari va ularning ta'siri	1121
Zuvaydullaev Nematullo Oybek o'g'li	
Роль управления производством в условиях модернизации экономики.....	1125
Гулов Мухтор Очилович	
Iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish sharoitida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining o'rni va ahamiyati	1129
To'rayev Shavkat Shuxratovich	
Роль цифрового маркетинга в продвижении туристических направлений.....	1136
Муродова Наргиза Уткировна	
Развитие финансовых рынков в странах СНГ: проблемы и перспективы.....	1140
Рузиев Зафар Икрамович, Каримов Ислон Ураз угли	
Современные инструменты продвижения бренда в условиях цифровой экономики.....	1145
Темирова Феруза Сагдуллаевна	
"Raqamli asrda axborot xavfsizligi: it texnologiyalar bilan xavfsizlikni ta'minlash yo'llari"	1149
Sherzod Rajabov	
Государственное регулирование инвестиционной деятельности: проблемы и направления совершенствования.....	1152
Шухрат Турсунов, Икромов Хасан Зафарович	
Economic incentives and barriers to sustainable transition in agribusiness: a comparative study of organic and conventional farming systems	1157
Mubina Toirova	
Цифровая трансформация банковской системы узбекистана: анализ внедрения fintech-решений в государственных банках	1162
Абдурахимова Дилора Каримовна	
Ta'lim muassasalaridagi ba'zi jihatlar	1167
A'zam Qutbiddin A'zam-zoda	
Klasterlar hisob siyosatida boshqaruv hisobining metodologik asoslari.....	1173
Toshpo'latov Azizbek Shermuxamadovich	
Egri soliqlarning mohiyati, genezisi va rivojlanish tendensiyalariga oid nazariy munozaralar xususida	1179
Shodiyev Olimjon Abduraxmonovich	
Ekologik mehmonhona faoliyatini rejalashtirish maqsadlari va vazifalari	1186
Abidova Dilfuza Igamberdievna	
Investitsiya loyihalarining iqtisodiy va moliyaviy samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	1200
Jo'rabekova Xumora Muzaffar qizi, Saidov Rasul Boltabayevich	
O'zbekistonda nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlarini moliyalashtirish manbalarining tahlili.....	1204
Aliyev Arslon Salom o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda turizm sohasining iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini statistik tahlil qilish.....	1213
Jumanova Zilola Tuychiyevna	
Xorijiy davlatlarda boylik solig'i va uning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	1219
Ruziyev G'anisher Usarovich	
Yer fondi va undan samarali foydalanishning nazariy asoslari (Samarqand viloyati misolida).....	1225
Xoshimova Sevara Baxromovna	
Iqtisodiy-ekologik tizimlarni boshqarishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning ilmiy asoslari	1229
Kuldoshev Asliddin Tursunovich	
Влияние финтех-услуг на финансовую инклюзию в сельских регионах узбекистана	1236
Абдурахимова Дилора Каримовна	
Surxondaryo viloyati sanoat sohasining asosiy ko'rsatkichlari tahlili.....	1240
Kuvanchiyeva Mehriniso Davlyatgeldi qizi	
A critical evaluation of strategic management's role in promoting sustainable development in Uzbekistan	1245
Ismatova Mahliyo	

O'zbekistonda turizm xizmatlari eksportini oshirishda zamonaviy infratuzilma va texnologiyalarning integratsiyasi.....	1251
Akmal Bakhromov	
Trends and reforms of corporate governance in state-owned enterprises.....	1257
F.Djalilov	
Переоценка долгосрочных активов в нефтегазовой промышленности и определение финансового результата от переоценки.....	1269
Махкамова Саида Гайратова	
Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari korxonalarini integratsiyalashuv jarayonlarini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirish.....	1275
Xodjiev Ibroxim Ikramovich	
Sug'urta kompaniyalari moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashning muhim shartlari.....	1280
Allanazarova B.K.	
P2P lending and crowdfunding as alternative sources of financing for small business in Uzbekistan.....	1286
Abdurakhimova Dilara Karimovna	
O'zbekistonda soliq nazoratining huquqiy va tashkiliy asoslarini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	1290
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Oymatova Gulnur Mirjamolovna	
Applications of hyperbolic geometry in physics and biology.....	1295
Khaknazarova Khurshidabonu Kenjaevna, Otakulova Rukhshona Akram kizi	
O'zbekiston temir yo'llari tizimining transformatsiyasi: modernizatsiya, raqamlashtirish va qayta tuzilish yo'nalishlari.....	1301
Nasrullayev Nurbek Baxtiyarovich	
The role of tourist product diversification in sustainable tourism development.....	1305
Raxmonov Shuxrat Shavkatovich, Alimova Mashhura Toirxonovna	
Temiryo'l transporti turi tavsifi.....	1310
Shodmonbekova Nodira Kamoljon qizi	
Kiberxavfsizlik: it infratuzilmasini himoya qilishning zamonaviy usullari.....	1321
D. Sh. Usmanbayev	
Mahalliy budjetlar daromad bazasini tahlili.....	1325
Qurbonov Nuriddin Ro'ziqulovich	
Развитие цифровых финансовых услуги в банковской системе Республики Узбекистан.....	1333
Абдурахманова Матлуба Махамдаминовна	
Avariya rejimlarida kichik yuklamali elektr ta'minoti tizimlarining kabel izolyatsiyasi monitoringini avtomatlashtirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari.....	1339
Mirzoyev Narzulla Nuriddinovich, Mamatqulov Toyir Chorshanbiyevich	
Analysis of increasing the speed of information exchange between the control interface and execution mechanisms in emergency mode in intelligent systems.....	1346
Azizbek Yusupbekov Nodirbekovich, Husniddin Esonov Mamarasul o'g'lu Assistant	
Sa'noat korxonalari va mexatron robotlarni optimal avtomatlashtirish va boshqarishda sun'iy intellektning ahamiyati.....	1351
Karabayev Ibragim Turdiyevich, Esonov Husniddin Mamarasul o'g'li, Abdullayeva Saodat Mengbayevna, Mamatqulov Toir Chorshanbiyevich	
Korxonaning moliyaviy holatini baholashda zamonaviy tahlil uslublarining qo'llanilishi.....	1355
Usmanova Nasiba Akbarjonovna, Suleymanova Asel Armanovna	
Xizmat ko'satish sohasida xotin-qizlar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar va raqamli texnologiyalarning ahamiyati.....	1360
Mirzayeva Shirin Nodirovna	
Rekreatsiya turizmi va sog'lomlashtirish xizmatlari integratsiyasi.....	1365
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatini rivojlantirishda ba'zi iqtisodiy yondashuvlarning nazariy jihatlarini.....	1369
Iskandarova D.B.	
Yashil (eko) investitsiyalarni tijorat banklari orqali moliyalashtirish.....	1373
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna	
Improvement of inventory accounting audit based on international standards.....	1378
Ovlayev Suhrob Temur o'g'li, Yo'ichiyev Oybek Ulug'bek o'g'li, Normo'minova Dilorom Umar qizi, Avlayeva Oybarchin Olim qizi	

Artificial intelligence systems for assessing creditworthiness	1382
Mardonova Durdona Yaxshiboy qizi	
B2B bozorini rivojlantirishda raqamli marketing texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni takomillashtirish	1387
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich	
Tech-driven growth and the economy of the future: brics-t in the society 5.0 paradigm	1395
Kaldibayev Nurlan Alimjanovich, Sagdullayeva Gulnora Botirovna, Durmanov, Akmal Shaimardanovich	
O'zbekistonda tabiiy resuslardan olinadigan rentaning yaimdagi ulushiga tanlab olingan o'zgaruvchilar ta'siri tahlili	1404
Tursunov Husnidin, Ibragimov Hasan	
O'zbekistonda fond bozorini tartibga solish	1412
Sultonov Sherali Nuraliyevich	
Public perception of the feasibility of introducing islamic banking in Uzbekistan: a consumer perspective	1418
Dr. Shamirova Surayo Kabildjanovna	
Directions for implementing the innovative digital technologies in tourism	1425
Norchaev Asatullo Norbutaevich	
Возможности совершенствования практики финансирования инвестиционных проектов	1430
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович, Хакимов Хафизбек Хамза угли	
O'zbekistonda pochta aloqasi xizmatlarini ko'rsatishning transport-logistika jarayonini mintaqaviy darajada rivojlantirish yo'llarini ishlab chiqish	1436
Palvanbayev Umidbek O'ktam o'g'li	
Aksiyalar qiymatini baholashning nazariy asoslari	1440
Botirxo'ja Aziza Faxmuddin qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni moliyalashtirishning rivojlanayotgan davlatlar amaliyoti tahlili	1444
Raimjanova Madina Asrarovna, Zokirova Feruza Farxod qizi	
Yashil loyihalarni davlat xususiy sheriklik asosida moliyalashtirish	1449
Zokirova Feruza Farxod qizi	
Факторы и риски, влияющие на оценку стоимости акции	1453
Батирхужа Азиза Фахмуддин кизи	
Финансовые риски в эпоху цифровой экономики: новые вызовы и способы управления	1458
Нуруллина Камила Рустамовна	
Tijorat banklarining yangi bank xizmatlarini iqtisodiy samaradorligi	1463
Rahmatov Temur Sotiboldiyevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish jarayonida ekologik innovatsiyalarning roli va amalga oshiruv mexanizmlari	1472
Ulichkina Lyudmila Ivanovna	
Эволюция профессиональных стандартов в республике узбекистан: от формирования к внедрению в сфере туризма	1478
Гольшева Елена Вячеславовна, Ивонина Наталья Викторовна	
Aligning uzbekistan's education reform with global best practices: the university of missouri as a model for systemic transformation	1485
Azamat Sulaymonov, Laylo Yakhshiboyeva	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklarining investision faolligini ta'minlash masalalari	1489
Axmedov Shoymurod Azamat o'g'li	
Kichik biznes subyektlarining iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlash masalasi	1493
Q.O.Tursunboyev	
Adoption of green economy mechanisms in the process of diversification of construction enterprises	1500
Yembergenova Aynur Aidosbayevna	
Nomoddiy aktivlar hisobini yuritish va audit jarayonlarini takomillashtirish yo'llari	1506
Rozmatova Umida Yuldashvna	
Raqamli moliya va uni sohaga joriy etish: innovatsion salohiyat	1512
Babadjanov Abdirashid Musayevich	
Влияние корпоративной культуры на инвестиционную стратегию промышленных предприятий	1527
Ёдгоров Сардорбек Самадович	

Jismoniy shaxslar kreditlarining bank portfeli sifatiga ta'siri: tahliliy yondashuv.....	1533
Sabirova Lobar Baxromovna	
Xo'jaligini soliqaqqa tortish mexanizmini samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	1539
Salimov Sherzod Baxtiyorovich	
Methods of improving customs management in transforming the customs bodies into a corruption-free field.....	1544
Mirzaxmedova Dilafuz Farxatovna, Tukhtabaev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich	
Особенности цифровизации налоговой системы в узбекистане.....	1548
Юсупов Одил Омонович	
Qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalarda texnologik yangiliklarni joriy etish: muammolar va imkoniyatlar.....	1554
Ismailov Akmal axsudovich, G'ulomov Ilhom Akramovich	
Kichik biznes subyektlarini kreditlashda raqamli bank xizmatlaridan foydalanishning afzalliklari.....	1560
Madjitova Maftuna Kamiljon qizi	
Tadbirkorlikda tavakkalchilikni boshqarishning nazariy asoslari.....	1564
Ziyatova Sitora Baxtiyorovna	
Importance of media activity in negotiations.....	1569
Fariza Xoldarova	
Kredit portfeli risklarini diversifikatsiya qilish strategiyalari.....	1575
Hamroyev Sherzod Axtamovich	
Marketing strategiyasi tushunchasi va uning turizm sohasidagi ahamiyati.....	1580
Komilov Dostonbek Ro'zimboy o'g'li	
Banklarining faoliyatini tartibga solish yo'llari.....	1586
Umirzoqova Aziza Olim qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sari: kanada tajribasi asosida o'zbekiston uchun istiqbollar.....	1590
Muratbaeva Eleonora Muxamedjan qizi, Norboyev Odil Abrayevich	
Aholi hayotiylik sifatining statistik tahlili.....	1595
Ostonaqulov Dilshod Ismatilla o'g'li	
Davlat moliyasini isloh qilish sharoitida budjet jarayonini takomillashtirish.....	1602
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li, Shamsitdinova Xonzoda Mardonbek qizi	
Recent trends in the global stock market: a macro-level analysis with emphasis on asia and central asia (2023–2025).....	1612
Mamataliev Bobur Saidnazar ugli	
Barqaror rivojlanishni ta'minlashda "yashil iqtisodiyot"ning o'rni.....	1617
Murodov Sardor Nurali o'g'li, Toxirov Shodiyor Zafar o'g'li	
Aholi daromadlari va ta'lim darajalarini turmush darajasiga ta'sirini baholash.....	1623
Xusinov I.I.	
Soliqlarni yig'iluvchanligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	1630
To'xsanov Qudratillo Nozimovich	
Qoraqalpog'iston respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatishni rivojlantirish muammolari.....	1635
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzoqovich, Tleymuratov Bahadir Genjemuratovich	
Forecasting and mitigating risks in international projects based on financial management principles.....	1641
Oripova Saodat Mirfotikh kizi	
Uglerod chiqindilarini buhgaletariya hisobiga integratsiya qilish: o'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida barqaror rivojlanish vositasi sifatida.....	1646
Halilov Sherzod Akhmatovich	
Contribution margin, dol, and break-even analysis: a financial performance comparison of amazon and walmart (2020–2024).....	1657
Kodir Gulomov	
Yashil iqtisodiyot: mohiyati, tushunchasi va rivojlanish tamoyillari.....	1664
Ataniyazova Maksuda Baltabayevna	
Beqarorlik sharoitida korxonalar ishlab chiqarish potensialidan foydalanishning optimallashtirish.....	1669
Jalilov Bahrom Sotiboldievich	
Innovatsion infratuzilmani rivojlantirish orqali xizmat sektorining raqobatbardoshligini hamda ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish.....	1674
Musinov Dilshod Sultanovich	

Davlat tibbiyot tashkilotlarida tovar – moddiy zaxiralar harakatini hujjatlashtirish.....	1680
Kuliboyev Azamat Shonazarovich	
Bank likvidligini boshqarishda valyuta kursi barqarorligini ta'minlash mexanizmlari.....	1686
Sattorova Nasiba G'anijon qizi	
Davlat xizmatlarining raqamlashuvi va tadbirkorlikka ta'siri.....	1690
Sattarov Xayrulla Fayzullayevich	
Iqtisodiy tizimda risk va uning xususiyatlari	1694
Nasimov Ravshanjon Azimovich	
Sanoat korxonasi faoliyatida ishlab chiqarish salohiyatining o'rni va roli.....	1701
Xudoyorova Mehrangiz Murodovna	
Xorijiy kapital va uning milliy iqtisodiyotdagi o'rni: nazariy-metodologik asoslar.....	1705
Abdullayev Zoxid Xolxo'jayevich	
Mahallalarda tadbirkorlikni va hunarmadchilikni rivojlantirishni boshqarishning ilmiy-nazariy jihatlari.....	1710
Tuxtasinov Zafarjon Odiljonovich	
Valyuta-moliya munosabatlari va globallashtirish jarayonlarining iqtisodiy mohiyati.....	1714
Gulmurodova Marjona Olimjon qizi, Jo'rabekova Xumora Muzaffar qizi, Yuldasheva Umida	
Tijorat banklarida aholi omonatlarini jalb qilish va ularning jozibadorligini oshirish strategiyalari: iqtisodiy va raqamli yondashuvlar	1719
Xakimov Zoxid Norbo'tayevich	
Davlat tibbiyot tashkilotlarida tovar – moddiy zaxiralar harakatini hujjatlashtirish.....	1725
Kuliboev Azamat Shonazarovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida inson kapitali sifatini oshirishda ta'limning ahamiyati.....	1731
M.Ostanova	
“Yashil” iqtisodiyotga o'tish davrida hududlar soliq salohiyatini va ularni oshirish masalalari	1736
Baxtiyorov Umid Kaxramon o'g'li	
Перспективы и инновационные подходы в методологии управления денежными потоками	1741
Машарипова Шахло Адамбаевна	
Soliq to'lovchilarning majburiyatlari bajarilishini ta'minlashning gnoseologik asoslari xususida	1746
Abdusherozov Abdullo Baxtiyorovich	
Mintaqaviy turizmni rivojlanishi va xavfsizligini ta'minlashda turizm infratuzilmasining o'rni va ahamiyati (xorazm viloyati timsolida)	1753
Doschanov Tangirbergen Doschanovich, Ruzmetova Shoira Shuxrat qizi	
Turizm destinatsiyalarida turistik mahsulotni yaratish jarayonining tahlili.....	1759
Tursunova Gulmira Rabbonovna	
Samarqand viloyatiga jalb qilingan investitsiyalarning tarkibiy tahlili.....	1764
Bektemirov Abdumalik Bektemirovich, Ergasheva Aziza Xasan qizi	
Davlat organlari ichki audit tuzilmalari tomonidan samaradorlik auditini tashkil etish masalalari.....	1773
Nasimov Fazliddin Sirojevich	
Совершенствование методологических основ внедрения цифровых финансовых активов.....	1777
Якубова Ш.Ш.	
O'zbekistonda turizm sohasi ko'rsatkichlari tahlili	1783
Ayubov Ilyos Ilxomovich	
“Yashil iqtisodiyot” ga o'tishda esg-lizingdan foydalanish xususiyatlari	1788
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratini kuchaytirishning nazariy asoslari va amaliy yo'nalishlari	1793
Kuliyev Komil Shuxratovich, A.Astanovulov	
Agrar sohani barqaror rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning ahamiyati	1798
Bazarov Nazirjon Sobirovich, Mo'minov Baxodir Orifjonovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida aloqa xizmatlarining iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash uslublari	1801
Xazratov Abror Panjiyevich	
Yengil sanoat eksportining mahsulot va geografik diversifikatsiyasi dinamikasi: muammo va yechimlar	1805
Umarkulov Kodirjon Maxamadaminovich, Abdunosirova Nilufar Ravshanbek qizi	

Yashil iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashning strategik yondashuvlari	1809
Toshboyev Bekzod Baxtiyorovich	
O'zbekistonda vino turizmini rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	1816
Jalilov Shoxjahon Xolbozor o'g'li	
Yashil startaplar samaradorligini aniqlashda raqamli vositalar roli	1820
Eshbayev Oybek Alik o'g'li	
Fuqarolik jamiyati institutlariga moliyaviy mablag' jalb etish yo'llari.....	1830
Po'latov Sardor Akmal o'g'li	
The importance of accounting policy in preparing reports based on international standards.....	1835
Sayfulloev Jamshid Qobil o'g'li	

THE IMPORTANCE OF ACCOUNTING POLICY IN PREPARING REPORTS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

Sayfulloev Jamshid Qobil o'g'li

Independent Researcher of TSUE, PhD

E-mail: sayfulloyevjamshid116@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0006-0391-7473

Abstract: This article provides insights into the importance of accounting policy in preparing reports based on international financial reporting standards and the tasks it addresses in accounting.

Key words: International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), International Accounting Standards (IAS), financial strategy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xalqaro moliyaviy hisobot standartlari asosida hisobotlarni tayyorlash jarayonida buxgalteriya siyosatining ahamiyati hamda uning buxgalteriya hisobida bajaradigan asosiy vazifalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Xalqaro moliyaviy hisobot standartlari (XMHS), Xalqaro buxgalteriya standartlari (XBS), moliyaviy strategiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение учетной политики при подготовке отчетности в соответствии с международными стандартами финансовой отчетности, а также задачи, которые она решает в бухгалтерском учете.

Ключевые слова: Международные стандарты финансовой отчетности (МСФО), Международные стандарты бухгалтерского учета (МСБУ), финансовая стратегия.

INTRODUCTION

The financial and economic information provided by business entities to both internal users (such as management, employees, and departments) and external users (including investors, creditors, regulatory bodies, and tax authorities) is typically prepared by the accounting department. The reliability, relevance, and accuracy of this information are directly influenced by the accounting policy adopted by the entity's management.

Accounting policy refers to the set of principles, rules, methods, and procedures that a company uses to record and report its financial transactions. It determines how income, expenses, assets, liabilities and equity are recognized, measured and disclosed in the financial statements. The more thoroughly and consistently the accounting policy is developed, the more reliable and useful the resulting information will be for decision-making. A well-structured accounting policy ensures that all accounting operations are carried out using a consistent and transparent approach, which enhances the comparability, clarity and integrity of financial reports. This in turn, helps users-both internal and external-make well-informed and confident decisions regarding the entity.

Conversely, if the accounting policy is poorly designed, inconsistently applied, or not aligned with applicable accounting standards and business practices, the financial reports may become misleading or inaccurate. This

can lead to incorrect decisions, regulatory issues, or a loss of trust among stakeholders.

Therefore, it is crucial for management and accounting professionals to carefully develop and implement an accounting policy that reflects the nature of the entity's operations, complies with legal and regulatory requirements, and supports transparency and accountability in financial reporting.

LITERATURE REVIEW

When preparing reports based on international standards, the rules of accounting policy and relevant regulatory legal acts have been adopted, and numerous studies have also been conducted by economists in this field.

In particular, according to IFRS 8, Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates, and Errors an organization's accounting policy *refers to specific principles, foundations, generally accepted conditions, rules, and practical approaches applied in the preparation and presentation of financial statements [1].

Elena Raisevich, in her research on this topic, emphasizes the importance of accounting policy and concludes: "Financial statements are the final product of the accounting information system, and when compiling them, methods and rules are introduced that have a varying impact on the figures presented. The choice of these methods and rules is the purpose of accounting policy. The quality of financial reporting is directly linked to the selected accounting policy" [2].

According to domestic scholars, such as Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor A.Z. Avlokulov, "Financial statements compiled based on international standards are essential for the effective management of business entities. The primary goal of transitioning to international standards is to enter global markets and attract investments. International standards also contribute significantly to the qualitative development of the national economy. In this process, a favorable investment climate, transparency of business entities, managerial accountability to shareholders, and the introduction of modern corporate governance practices play a key role in the development of joint-stock companies" [3].

B.N. Sayfutdinov, who conducted research on the development of accounting policies in line with the requirements of international financial reporting standards, came to the following conclusion: "Accounting policy includes a set of rules, methods, and principles used in accounting by any economic entity during the reporting period. A rational and consistent accounting policy structure enhances the reliability and transparency of financial reporting" [4]. The aforementioned points clearly underscore the critical role that accounting policy plays in organizing the operations of the accounting service of an economic entity. In our view, accounting policy is not only vital for the organization of accounting operations, but also significantly influences other functional areas of the entity's overall economic activity.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research approach based on the analysis of primary and secondary sources. The primary focus is on examining international financial reporting standards (IFRS) and relevant regulatory frameworks that define and influence accounting policies. Data for the research were collected through:

A literature review of scholarly articles, IFRS standards (particularly IFRS 8), and national accounting regulations.

Comparative analysis of expert opinions and practices from both international and domestic accounting environments.

Content analysis of selected financial statements to assess the impact of accounting policy choices on the reliability and transparency of financial reporting.

This methodology allows for a comprehensive understanding of how accounting policy affects financial reporting quality and compliance under international standards.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the important functions of accounting is control. According to Article 21 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Accounting", "Internal control is a system of measures organized on the basis of the accounting policy adopted by the head of the accounting entity in order to ensure the legality and economic feasibility of economic operations, the safety of assets, and the prevention and detection of cases of embezzlement and errors in the maintenance of accounting records, as well as the preparation of financial and other reports." Indeed, accounting provides property owners with reliable information about the state of their assets by monitoring their efficient and lawful use.

Let us examine the tasks that accounting policy addresses within the accounting system (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Tasks solved by accounting in business entities

The next important task of accounting is the planning of financial strategy.

The information generated by accounting service employees forms the basis for accurately determining the financial strategy by enabling proper planning of activities for upcoming years, including forecasting the quantity of products to be produced and delivered to customers.

Optimal use of resources is another key objective of accounting.

Employees of the accounting service are required to regularly provide management with reports regarding the rational use of fixed assets, inventories, and financial resources available to the entity. Based on this information, decisions can be made to prevent fraudulent activity and to timely identify missed opportunities for efficient asset utilization. Financial and management accounting information allows for the assessment of critical performance indicators. Financial indicators are derived from the balance sheet, the statement of financial results, and the statement of cash flows. Meanwhile, management accounting provides additional metrics, including labor productivity, capital productivity, capital intensity, material productivity, material intensity, and other related indicators.

In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 207 dated July 28, 2015, titled "On the Introduction of Criteria for Assessing the Effectiveness of Joint-Stock Companies and Other Economic Entities with State Participation," enterprises within the energy system-being the subject of this research-submit their key performance indicators to the State Assets Management Agency within the prescribed timeframe.

Reliable accounting information eliminates subjectivity in economic decision-making. This is because, in accounting, all transactions are documented and summarized based on those documents. The accuracy of the data recorded in the documents is the responsibility of the accountant and is regularly monitored by the chief accountant and the internal auditor.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As a result of the study, the analyzed situations were summarized and the following conclusions and proposals were formulated:

The quality of accounting work in business entities is directly related to the accounting policy adopted within them. Accounting policy plays a crucial role in organizing accounting procedures in economic entities, monitoring enterprise activities, ensuring the rational use of resources, and developing sound financial strategies.

The application of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) is essential for maintaining consistency and systematization in the provisions of accounting policies. IFRS are currently utilized by many countries around the world and serve as a vital instrument in conducting foreign economic activities and establishing strong international partnerships. The requirements of these standards are clear, reliable, and significantly contribute to the generation of trustworthy and transparent financial information.

REFERENCES

1. International Accounting Standards; International Financial Reporting Standards. <https://www.ifrs.org>
2. Raičević, J. (2021). Accounting policies as a function of quality assessment of financial statements. *Economic Themes*, 59(3), 357-373. <https://doi.org/10.2478/ethemes-2021-0021>
3. Avlokulov, A. Z. (2019). Improvement of the Methodology of Accounting and Auditing of Financial Results (Doctoral dissertation abstract, Doctor of Economic Sciences). Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 72 p.
4. Sayfutdinov, B. N. (2023). Improvement of Compilation and Audit of Financial Statements in Joint-Stock Companies (Doctoral dissertation abstract, PhD in Economics). Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 56 p.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 5

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
